

IMPROVING SOFTWARE FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' DIGITAL LITERACY THROUGH INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION

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Abstract. *This article discusses the need to enhance software aimed at developing students' digital literacy through interdisciplinary integration, using modern information and communication technologies. It analyzes methodological approaches that ensure the interconnection of various academic disciplines to support the development of digital literacy in the educational process. The paper outlines ways to foster students' skills in critical thinking, information analysis, and problem-solving in a digital environment through interactive platforms, electronic resources, and a networked learning environment. The proposed software models are developed based on interdisciplinary relationships and are pedagogically validated through practical implementation.*

Keywords: *Digital literacy, interdisciplinary integration, software, interactive learning, information and communication technologies, networked learning environment.*

Introduction

In the era of globalization and digital transformation, one of the priority tasks facing the higher education system is the formation of digital literacy of students and its systemic development based on interdisciplinary integration. Digital literacy is an important competence that allows a student to independently search for information using modern technologies, analyze, process it and make informed decisions. Interactive software plays a key role in this process. This article analyzes the currently used software tools and those that require improvement for the development of digital literacy of students based on an interdisciplinary approach.

1. Theoretical foundations of the subject content

Pedagogical essence of the digital literacy competence

Concept	Definition	Scientific source	Role in the learning process
Digital literacy	The student's ability to search, analyze, process, and safely use information using digital technologies	UNESCO (2021), OECD (2020)	Independent reading, decision-making, reflection
Interdisciplinary integration	The process of creating complex knowledge through the substantive and methodological integration of various disciplines	Mavlonova (2022)	Real-life assignments, STEAM projects
PBL (Problem-Based Learning)	Learning based on a problem situation	Barrows (1986)	Analytical and decision-making skills

Concept	Definition	Scientific source	Role in the learning process
IBL (Inquiry-Based Learning)	Learning through questioning and inquiry	Dewey (1938)	Research skills, hypothesis development
AKT (ICT)	A set of technologies for searching, storing, processing and transmitting information	Kodirov & Rakhmonova (2022)	Distance learning, interactivity, individualization

Digital literacy is a set of functional skills of a student that allow him to search for information using digital technologies, analyze it, process it with digital tools, present the results and safely navigate the digital environment. Formation of this competence based on an interdisciplinary approach is one of the urgent tasks of modern education. The development of this competence is based on the following main pedagogical and theoretical sources:

The theory of constructivism (J. Piaget, L.S. Vygotsky): knowledge is formed on the basis of the student's own experience. Independent acquisition of knowledge using digital tools within the framework of interdisciplinary projects and assignments deepens this process.

Activity theory (A.N. Leontiev): the acquisition of knowledge is the result of active actions of the subject. Students participate in the processes of active search, analysis and evaluation in the digital environment.

Metacognitive theory: the student is aware of and controls his thought process. This is an important factor in improving digital literacy, in particular, for assessing one's own activities, reflection and creating digital portfolios.

The Role of Software and Its Theoretical Framework

From a theoretical perspective, digital technologies and software tools play an important role in the personalization, adaptation, and integration of education across disciplines. Interactive platforms (such as Moodle, Google Classroom, Edmodo, Canva, Padlet) provide the following capabilities:

Interactivity: students engage in interdisciplinary digital activities and strengthen their knowledge through active discussion, problem solving, and idea sharing;

Visualization: in-depth analysis of information is provided through graphs, tables, videos, and animations;

Flexibility: each student works at an individual pace and assignments are presented in an individual format, which promotes the development of digital literacy;

Interdisciplinary compatibility: providing resources across disciplines in a unified manner enhances integration.

Therefore, through interactive, multifunctional software tools supported by theoretical foundations, students are formed as digital, analytical, and critically thinking digital citizens.

Base type	Features	Pedagogical task
Theoretical foundations	Constructivism, activity theory, metacognition, TPACK	It defines the ideological foundation of the educational process.
Practical foundations	Platforms (Moodle, Classroom, Edmodo), gamification, AI recommendations	Engages the student in real-world digital activities

2. Practical foundations of the content of science

2.1. Platforms used in practice and their capabilities

Platform	Advantages	Limitations	Practical example
Moodle	Open source, with extensive course management capabilities	Simple design, complex user interface	Designing interdisciplinary courses
Google Classroom	Designing interdisciplinary courses	No multi-function monitoring	Biology + Computer Science Joint Assignments
Edmodo	Working in a social network style, interactivity is strong	Lower security level	History + Art Project Discussion
Kahoot/Quizizz	Game-based tests and quizzes	Cannot analyze the theory in depth	STEAM quizzes

Digital platforms that support interdisciplinary integration play an important role in developing digital literacy. The following modern platforms are widely used to develop students' learning, independent work and digital skills:

The name of the platform	Description
Moodle	An open source platform that allows you to create courses, work with tests, assignments, and forums
Google Classroom	A convenient environment for sharing files, assignments, and assessments between teacher and student
Edmodo	A platform that supports interdisciplinary interactive learning, working in a social network style
Kahoot / Quizizz	Consolidate knowledge in an interesting way through digital tests, interdisciplinary quizzes, and game elements

These tools allow the student to practically develop their digital information skills, collaboration, analysis, and presentation.

2.2. Areas for software improvement

To deepen interdisciplinary integration and more effectively develop digital literacy, it is necessary to integrate the following modern technological solutions into existing platforms:

AI-powered recommendation system — offers the student personalized learning recommendations (e.g. additional materials, exercises on obscure topics) that match their level of knowledge.

Gamification elements — increasing student motivation with points, ratings, badges, and certificates.

Progress monitoring — displaying each student's learning status with graphs and statistics, providing analytical data to the teacher.

Reflection module — providing the student with the opportunity to express their thoughts and conclusions in a digital format and evaluate the learning process.

These functions contribute to the development of students' independence, digital critical thinking and interdisciplinary thinking.

2.3. Practical experience and problems of Uzbekistan

Digital educational platforms are also being implemented in higher education institutions of Uzbekistan. In particular, there are systems such as "ZiyoNet", "Testportali.uz" and "I-Test".

From these platforms, the possibility of organizing independent learning has been created, especially in the form of testing. However, most of the existing systems are focused only on control and assessment, that is, most of them lack creative, interactive and analytical components that develop digital literacy.

Therefore, the development and implementation of complex platforms aimed at developing interdisciplinary, integrated and digital thinking is considered an urgent task.

3. Pedagogical approaches focused on learning based on problem situations and scientific activity

3.1. Problem-based learning (PBL) in the development of digital literacy

In the interdisciplinary integrated educational process, the problem-based approach to learning serves as an important methodological basis for the development of students' digital literacy. From this approach, students develop such digital and critical competencies as independent research, analysis of information in digital tools, development of solutions and construction of substantiated conclusions.

The model of problem-based learning is based on the following pedagogical theoretical foundations:

Constructivism: knowledge is formed by the student on the basis of his own active experience, that is, the student acts independently when solving digital problems;

Activity theory (A.N. Leontiev): the process of obtaining knowledge is based on active thinking;

Experiential learning: learning occurs on the basis of real-life situations, which allows applying the acquired knowledge in practice.

The main principles of problem-based learning in the digital context:

Student-centered approach - takes into account how each student processes digital information;

Realistic situations – based on real problems of digital learning (case studies, role-playing games, modeling digital scenarios);

Teamwork and collaboration – joint analysis of interdisciplinary problems in groups;

Teacher-facilitator – participates in the process as a guide, consultant, does not provide ready-made answers.

Practical example (based on an interdisciplinary problem):

Students are offered the following interdisciplinary problem situation:

"What software platform can be developed to develop digital literacy in the interdisciplinary learning process?"

Students independently study the problem, going through the following stages:

1. Problem analysis – assessing the level of digital literacy, identifying existing problems;
2. Information collection – studying local and foreign experience using digital tools;
3. Solution development – developing proposals based on AI, visualization, gamification, designing interdisciplinary modules;

4. Conclusions and proposals – decision-making based on factual data and project presentation.

This approach promotes the development of digital literacy not only as knowledge, but also as a practical activity and critical thinking skills.

3.2. Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL)

Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL)– a research-based educational methodology – is a very effective pedagogical model for developing digital literacy based on an interdisciplinary approach. This approach forms the student’s activity in searching for knowledge based on their own questions, independent study of digital sources, hypotheses and their analysis. IBL is based on the methodology of scientific research and educates students as independent scientific thinkers and decision makers based on factual data.

The stages of IBL are manifested in the digital context as follows:

1. Problem identification – posing real digital problems that exist in an interdisciplinary field (e.g., “How can digital visualization be more effective in biology lessons?”).
2. Formulating a hypothesis – forming preliminary ideas about a solution using digital tools.
3. Data collection – collecting information through online resources, electronic libraries, interactive platforms.
4. Analysis and conclusion – testing the hypothesis using digital analysis tools (graphs, diagrams, statistical modules).
5. Report or presentation – presenting the final results in digital form in the form of presentations, infographics, video reports.

Benefits in the context of digital literacy:

Critical and systemic thinking skills are developed – the student bases his/her reasoning on reliable digital data;

The ability to think and reason in scientific language is formed, especially using interdisciplinary terms and electronic academic resources;

Independent knowledge assessment – individual knowledge assessment based on digital experience, projects and analysis.

Therefore, the IBL approach deepens students’ digital literacy and increases their ability for interdisciplinary thinking, guiding them to independent scientific research in the digital environment.

3.3. Integration of problem-based and scientific approaches

The comprehensive integration of problem-based learning (PBL) and inquiry-based learning (IBL) approaches in the formation of interdisciplinary digital literacy increases the effectiveness of education. The combination of these two methodologies allows students to identify digital problems, analyze them, make scientifically based decisions and present the results in digital tools.

In modern digital education, this integrated approach is implemented as follows:

Mini-research projects - students analyze real-life problem situations using electronic resources in an interdisciplinary context;

Research laboratories - in remote or digital laboratories, digital literacy issues related to the subject are studied using the scientific method;

Project-based e-learning - a project-based digital learning process on electronic platforms, within which students present their research in an interactive form.

Due to this approach, students learn not only to use digital tools, but also to make independent decisions based on interdisciplinary scientific and analytical thinking and interconnection.

3.4. Application of PBL/IBL approaches using software

Specially adapted digital platforms play an important role in the effective implementation of PBL (problem-based learning) and IBL (research-based learning) methods. The following tools are useful for developing students' digital literacy and interdisciplinary competencies:

The name of the platform Opportunities

Padlet	Brainstorming, problem mapping, visual analysis
Trello	Managing the stages of scientific research, distributing tasks within the group
Miro / Jamboard	Problem mapping, cause-and-effect diagrams, teamwork
Google Scholar	Search and use of scientific articles, evidence, theoretical foundations
Notion	Research diary, task planning, preparation of final reports

From these platforms, students will strengthen their skills in collecting, analyzing information, digital documentation, collaboration and presentation. This will allow them to direct their digital literacy towards solving real-life problems in an interdisciplinary context.

4. The possibility of ensuring interdisciplinary connections and mutual harmony

4.1. The concept and necessity of interdisciplinary integration

Interdisciplinary integration in the formation of digital literacy is the process of developing a student's comprehensive knowledge and skills by harmonizing natural connections between different disciplines using digital tools. This approach is based on constructivist pedagogy, a systems approach and a competency-based education model.

The main goals of interdisciplinary integration are:

Teaching natural sciences not in isolation, but in the context of real life and practice - for example, visual modeling in biology, analytical graphics in mathematics and economics; Developing students' ability to solve complex problems based on an interdisciplinary approach (searching for information, analyzing it, justifying and presenting the result) is one of the important elements of digital literacy.

In this process, digital tools – interactive platforms, project programs, artificial intelligence tools, analytical panels – act as a link between disciplines.

4.2. Compatibility of digital literacy and interdisciplinary approach

To develop students' digital literacy on an interdisciplinary basis, it is necessary to ensure substantive and functional compatibility between different academic disciplines. The table below presents the main disciplines and their direct connection with digital literacy:

Science type	Source of harmony
Information Technology	Independently search for information on digital media, code, and create graphics
Pedagogy	Developing self-management, reflection, and metacognitive analysis skills
Psychology	Motivation, self-awareness, and independent decision-making in the digital environment
Language and speech culture	Working with text information, preparing digital documents, making presentations

Science type	Source of harmony
Research methodology	Collecting scientific information, analyzing digital sources, hypothesizing, drawing conclusions

This integration forms the student’s interdisciplinary digital competencies. In particular: Technical, analytical, research, verbal and pedagogical skills are developed together; Digital literacy is formed through interdisciplinary interaction in a multi-contextual, creative and reflective approach;

The software supports this interdisciplinary integration with digital tools in a visual, interactive and modular form.

4.3. Technological tools that ensure an interdisciplinary approach

Technological tools play a decisive role in the development of digital literacy through an interdisciplinary approach. They allow combining different disciplines, creating mutually adapted tasks, organizing interaction and evaluating the final results. The following modern platforms create broad opportunities for the implementation of interdisciplinary integration in educational practice:

Tool / Platform	Opportunities
Microsoft Teams / Google Workspace	Management of interdisciplinary project teams, document exchange, organization of integrated lessons
Trello / Notion	Planning and organizing tasks and phases that consist of several disciplines
Padlet / Miro	Creating cross-topic mind maps, conceptual models, and cause-and-effect diagrams
Kahoot / Quizizz	Create interdisciplinary quizzes, integrated tests, and assessment exercises

From these tools, students develop not only digital skills, but also interdisciplinary interaction, systems thinking, and digital expression of their ideas.

4.4. Examples of Practical Integration

The following forms of practical integration are effective for developing an interdisciplinary approach based on digital literacy:

STEAM projects (*Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, Mathematics*): within this approach, students combine several disciplines and develop a digital solution to a problem using an integrated approach. For example, a physics lesson explains the operating principle of a device, a computer science lesson practices its modeling in a visual program, a fine arts lesson practices interface design, and a mathematics lesson practices calculations.

Independent project work: students analyze a selected topic from pedagogical, technological, and psychological points of view using digital tools. During this process, they develop skills in collecting, analyzing, creating infographics, and presenting information.

Portfolio Methodology: An interdisciplinary approach is used to collect projects, graphic designs, video reports and textual analyses through digital platforms, demonstrating the student’s self-assessment and development.

From to these practical approaches, digital literacy becomes a practical skill rather than an abstract concept, and students are prepared to solve real-world problems using interdisciplinary knowledge.

4.5. Benefits of Interdisciplinary Integration

Formation of digital literacy based on an interdisciplinary approach allows not only to impart knowledge within individual disciplines, but also to master it through an integrated approach close to real life. Such integration provides the following benefits:

Understanding the relationship between knowledge is facilitated – the student understands the connection between information technology, analytical methods and content disciplines;

Development of systems thinking – the habit of analyzing complex problems from an interdisciplinary point of view is formed;

Ability to approach complex issues from different scientific perspectives – biological, technological, psychological, social factors are analyzed together using digital tools;

Education is created that is adapted to practical life – the student has the opportunity to transform the acquired knowledge into digital solutions in real conditions.

5. Consolidation of knowledge through practical training

5.1. Pedagogical essence of practical training

Practical training plays an important role in deepening digital literacy and implementing interdisciplinary integration in practice. These classes help to consolidate theoretical knowledge in situations close to real life. In particular, they help to develop the skills of independent work in the digital environment, creative thinking and the use of technology.

As part of practical training, students actively develop the following competencies:

Independent thinking – solving problems with an individual approach;

Decision making – choosing the most effective of a variety of digital solutions;

Creative approach – creating digital projects, presentations, content;

Practical skills – working with technology platforms, data analysis, visualization and output of results.

These activities are pedagogically based on the active learning model and promote progression through the higher levels of Bloom's taxonomy - application, analysis, synthesis, evaluation. It is possible to implement these stages interactively, especially through digital platforms (Moodle, Notion, Miro, Padlet, Canva, etc.).

5.2. The relationship between independent work competence and practical activities

Competency element	Practical training type	Tools
Search information	for Online research, bibliographic analysis	Google Scholar, Ziyonet
Decision-making	Case study, problem situation	Miro, Padlet
Creative thinking	Interdisciplinary project, infographic	Canva, Figma
Collaboration	Group discussion, role-playing games	Trello, MS Teams
Reflection	Portfolios, blogging	Notion, WordPress

The competence of independent work occupies a central place in the formation of digital literacy. The formation of this competence is ensured through an educational environment integrated with direct practical activities. The following table presents the elements of independent work in a digital context and the associated forms of practical training:

Competency element	Suitable practical training format
Search for information	Use of online research, bibliographic analysis, digital libraries and scholarly platforms
Decision making	Case study, analysis of problem situations through digital visualization
Creative thinking	Interdisciplinary project work, design-based assignments (using Canva, Figma, Prezi)
Communication and cooperation	Team discussions, role-playing games, and collaboration on virtual platforms
Planning and analysis	Gantt chart, SWOT analysis, KPI tracking (via Trello, Notion, Miro)

Therefore, each element of digital competence is formed more deeply in connection with practical activities and strengthens the digital literacy of the student.

5.3. Types and methods of practical classes

The methodology of practical classes for the development of interdisciplinary integration and digital literacy is based on this approach. The following types of classes are used in combination with modern educational technologies:

1. Mini-projects

- Students work in small groups on a specific interdisciplinary problem. This process requires the analysis of digital sources and the presentation of the results in the form of infographics or video presentations.

2. Modeling

- An activity aimed at making decisions in a situation close to real life. For example, the situation of creating an online educational platform is modeled, and students act in different roles (analyst, designer, user).

3. Data-based analysis

- Students analyze information and draw conclusions based on statistical tables, graphs and other digital resources (Excel, Google Sheets, Tableau). This process develops critical thinking.

4. Elements of Industrial Practice

- Developing models of manufacturing or service processes based on digital simulation. Students simulate activities in areas such as digital printing, e-commerce, and educational platforms.

These approaches allow for the development of digital literacy through practical classes, the implementation of interdisciplinary knowledge, and the preparation of students for the creation of integrated solutions.

5.4. Organizing Practical Classes Using Digital Tools

Organizing practical classes using digital technologies is of great importance in developing digital literacy in interdisciplinary integrated education. Classes conducted using these tools are interactive, visual, and collaborative, and allow students to gain knowledge close to the real environment.

The following tools and applications allow for the effective organization of practical classes in a digital environment:

Tool / Application	Implementation options
Canva / Figma	Creating digital design, visual presentations, infographics, and creative project work
Google Forms	Online tests, questionnaires, automatic assessment systems
Padlet / Miro	Mind maps, cause-and-effect analyses, team conceptual development
Excel / Google Sheets	Analytical work based on statistics, reports, graphs and numerical tables
Zoom / Microsoft Teams	Online simulations, role-playing games, group discussions, presentations

These platforms will enable students to implement real projects in a digital environment, exchange ideas and demonstrate results. This strengthens the practical components of digital literacy.

5.5. Effectiveness and measurement mechanisms

Criterion	High level	Intermediate level	Low level
Information quality	The evidence is sound, the sources are diverse.	Primary sources used	Limited, general information
Analytical thinking	Logical, evidence-based conclusions	Partially consistent	Superficial, without proof
Digital solution	Interactive, practical	Simple, it works	Partially working
Collaboration	Active in the group, roles are clear	Partially distributed	Passive
Reflection	Deep, measured	Descriptive	No

Criteria-based approach and indicator-based analysis are important for assessing the effectiveness of digital literacy developed during practical classes. The following indicators help to accurately assess the effectiveness of educational activities:

Quality of the final product (e.g. project, visual presentation, video, analytical report) – assesses how the student applies digital and interdisciplinary knowledge;

Level of participation and initiative – students are assessed through group roles, active discussion and periodic feedback;

Reflexive analysis – students analyze their work after completing the exercise and express their feedback in writing or orally;

Criterion-based analysis using assessment paper – each element of competence (e.g. design quality, information analysis, digital presentation format) is assessed using assessment rubrics based on specific criteria.

This assessment system ensures the assessment of not only the final result, but also the activity itself in the educational process. As a result, an objective, open and transparent assessment mechanism is created in the development of digital literacy.

6. Implementation of information and communication technologies in the educational process

6.1. The concept of information and communication technologies (ICT) and their role in education

Information and communication technologies (ICT) are considered the main tool for developing digital literacy and ensuring interdisciplinary integration. ICT is a set of technical and software tools designed to search, store, process, transmit and present information.

In the modern educational process, ICT creates the following pedagogical opportunities:

Interactivity - lessons are enriched with multimedia, interactive platforms, digital resources;

Individualization - the student has the opportunity to choose an independent educational path corresponding to his level of knowledge;

Distance learning - the ability to gain knowledge anywhere and anytime (via Zoom, Google Meet, learning management systems);

Independent work environment - allows the student to search, analyze, present and evaluate in the digital environment.

Therefore, ICT becomes a three-stage pedagogical tool, acting as a condition, means and result of the development of digital literacy.

6.2. *The main functions of ICT in education and forms of their implementation*

The table below presents the main functions of information and communication technologies in the educational process and the forms of their implementation. They directly contribute to the formation of digital literacy based on an interdisciplinary approach:

Task	Implementation form
Expanding knowledge acquisition	Electronic libraries (ZiyoNet, JSTOR), online courses, video lectures, podcasts
Develop analysis	Data visualization tools (Tableau, Excel charts), statistical analysis programs
Improving computer literacy	Perform tasks and create documents using Microsoft Word, Excel, PowerPoint
Support for independent work	Testing systems, LMS platforms (Moodle, Google Classroom, Edmodo)
Strengthening communication	Organize collaboration through forums, online chats, group discussions, video conferences

The educational process organized using ICT tools not only strengthens digital literacy, but also becomes the main tool for developing students' interdisciplinary analysis, creative thinking, and independent decision-making competencies.

6.3. *Types of ICT tools*

ICT tools used to develop digital literacy have various functional areas and support each stage of the educational process. The main ICT tools that help strengthen students' interdisciplinary knowledge in the digital environment are listed below:

1. Educational platforms — Moodle, Edmodo, Coursera, Khan Academy

Allow you to create courses, assign tasks, organize testing, and establish interaction between teachers and students.

2. Multimedia tools — PowerPoint, Canva, Animaker, Genially

Develop students' creative and visual literacy by creating digital presentations, infographics, animations, and visual materials.

3. Online communication tools – Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Google Meet

Serve as effective platforms for group discussions, situational modeling, idea sharing and presentations.

4. Assessment systems – Google Forms, Quizizz, Socrative

Allow for criteria-based assessment of students' knowledge level using online tests, quick surveys and automatic output of results.

5. Artificial intelligence-based systems – ChatGPT, Grammarly, DeepL

Deepen digital literacy by being a tool for text analysis, translation, editing of written speech and intellectual assistance.

The combined use of these tools allows for the development of digital literacy in technical, cognitive and communicative spheres.

6.4. Forms of ICT use in education

The use of ICT is not only a technological convenience, but also a methodological approach. Thanks to them, the learning process can be personalized, flexible and integrated. The following formats are particularly suitable for developing digital literacy in an interdisciplinary context:

Hybrid (blended) education. Integrates traditional lessons with assignments, assessments, presentations, and the use of online resources in a digital environment. For example, class discussions and video analysis or a digital project at home.

Distance learning. Organizes learning activities without geographical restrictions. This method allows organizing student learning using platforms such as LMS, Zoom, Microsoft Teams.

Virtual labs allow for modeling, simulating experiments, and calculating in STEM, natural sciences, economic analysis, and other technological areas.

Digital portfolio. Allows you to store, track, and evaluate all student practical work, presentations, analytical documents, projects, and reflective essays in a digital format.

From to these formats, students not only carry out their learning activities in a digital environment, but also learn to understand interdisciplinary connections and effectively apply them to solving real-world problems.

6.5. Practical integration experience

In Uzbekistan and around the world, there are a number of best practices for the successful use of information and communication technologies in the development of an interdisciplinary approach and digital literacy. This experience allows developing independent work skills, creating personalized learning spaces and ensuring interdisciplinary integration of education through the introduction of digital solutions into the education system.

Practical experience of Uzbekistan

Platforms such as Moodle, Ziyonet and TestPortal are actively being implemented in many universities of the republic, providing students with the opportunity for distance learning, testing, electronic materials and assignments.

Digitalization of the assessment process through the Electronic Journal and Electronic Assessment systems simplifies the interaction of teachers and students and expands the analysis capabilities.

Nowadays, some universities are testing automated assessment systems based on artificial intelligence. These systems allow for an accurate analysis of student work and the development of individual recommendations.

Advanced international experience

The Finnish education system is one of the leading in the world. In this country, 80% of education is organized using ICT. Students use interactive tools, online platforms and digital labs to learn.

Schools in Singapore have launched personalized learning paths powered by AI. Each student is provided with a personalized digital learning path based on their level of knowledge, interests and learning characteristics using customized digital assessment, analysis and guidance algorithms.

The given practical examples show that the educational model organized using ICT and AI tools allows not only to form digital literacy, but also to transform it into an interdisciplinary, flexible, active and effective educational system.

6.6. Advantages and problems of using information and communication technologies

The wide use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the development of digital literacy of students improves the quality and efficiency of the educational process. At the same time, the capabilities of ICT are accompanied by a number of problems. The main advantages and existing problems of using ICT in the process of interdisciplinary integration based on digital education are highlighted below:

Advantages:

Permanent access to education - thanks to ICT, students have the opportunity to access educational materials, electronic libraries, video lectures and tests at any time;

Flexibility and personalization of learning - on digital platforms, it becomes possible to individually adjust educational tasks, create a learning trajectory suitable for each student;

Opportunities for analysis and reflection — thanks to ICT, students develop skills in assessing their own effectiveness, using digital tools and analyzing results;

Availability of an online environment for collaboration — group projects, forums and video discussions provide an opportunity for interdisciplinary exchange of ideas and collective decision-making.

Challenges:

Digital inequality — for some students, lack of access to high-quality Internet and the availability of modern devices limits their full participation in digital education;

Insufficient level of technological literacy — low level of ICT skills (especially among some teachers) hinders the effective use of digital tools;

Low motivation — when both students and teachers are insufficiently interested in digital education and have insufficient internal motivation, the process of mastering the material slows down;

Difficulty of control in virtual learning — in digital classes based on independent work, there are difficulties in ensuring academic integrity and realistically assessing participation.

In conclusion:

The availability of ICT is a decisive factor in the formation of digital literacy of students, but their effective use requires a systematic approach to infrastructure, methodology and motivation.

7. Diversity of tools used in training

7.1. The nature and functional role of educational tools

In the formation of digital literacy, educational tools are one of the main components of the learning process. They play an important role in the formation of knowledge and skills, linking them with practice, activating collaborative learning and analytical thinking. Especially in the

interdisciplinary integrated learning model, the diversity of tools comprehensively develops digital competencies.

The main functions of educational tools:

Visualization and simplification of the learning process - clear and visual explanation of theoretical concepts;

Increased student engagement - active expression of opinions through interactive tools, participation in group discussions;

Linking theory with practice - through projects, simulations and digital assignments;

Activation of independent thinking and analytical skills through questions, reflection and assessment.

7.2. Classification of educational tools

Tools used in interdisciplinary educational activities are divided into the following types depending on their functions and technological level:

The type of vehicle Samples

Traditional	Blackboard, markers, visual aids, sheets, charts
Technical	Projector, television, tape recorder, microscope
Digital	Computer, tablet, mobile applications, LMS systems (Moodle, Edmodo)
Interactive	Touch screen, electronic whiteboard, simulation programs (Miro, Labster)
Multimedia	Video, animation, audio lessons, 3D modeling tools (Animaker, Genially)

Each tool has its own role and purpose, and their correct and harmonious use increases the effectiveness of learning.

7.3. Ensuring the harmonious use of tools during the lesson

The conscious and gradual integration of tools is very important for the development of digital literacy through interdisciplinary integration. The following set of tools is used in the classes:

1. Introductory stage – Visual and interactive materials for presenting the topic:

Introductory video, slides with questions and answers (PowerPoint, Mentimeter, Prezi)

2. Main stage – Analysis of problem situations and project work:

Trello – task distribution, Miro – problem map, Notion – project diary

3. Consolidation stage – Knowledge testing and assessment:

Google Forms – tests, Kahoot/Quizizz – interactive assessment based on a test

4. Reflection stage – Expression, assessment and analysis of one's own opinion:

Padlet – written reflection, Jamboard – group conclusion, whiteboard

This approach not only ensures that students fully master digital tools, but also activates creative and critical thinking at each stage.

7.4. Artificial intelligence and new generation tools

Interdisciplinary integrated learning processes, AI-based tools are increasingly used to deepen digital literacy. These tools are characterized by personalized, flexible and multifunctional capabilities. They play an important role in motivating students to explore independently and engaging them in written, oral and visual work. The following are the functions of modern artificial intelligence tools in the learning process:

The name of the vehicle Function

ChatGPT	Answering questions, analyzing text, developing ideas, creating written assignments
Khanmigo Academy)	(Khan Explanations, simplification of questions, interactive guidance as a personal tutor
Grammarly LanguageTool	/ Editing written text, identifying grammatical errors, and making suggestions
DALL-E / Canva AI	Creating visual materials, infographics, and illustrations using artificial intelligence

These tools provide students with not only visual or audio support, but also the opportunity to independently analyze, work creatively, and work in an environment focused on deepening knowledge.

7.5. Benefits of working with different tools

Using a combination of different tools and technologies in education not only improves the quality of the lesson, but also creates the basis for the natural application of an interdisciplinary approach. In particular, a wide range of digital literacy tools provides the following pedagogical benefits:

Lessons become interactive and lively - students are involved in the educational process visually, auditorily, and kinesthetically;

It is easier to maintain student attention - digital transformations, visual materials, and interactive tasks ensure a high level of attention during the lesson;

It is possible to work with students of different levels of intelligence - artificial intelligence and adaptive tools allow for an individual approach to each student;

Multichannel learning is provided - deep assimilation of knowledge through visual, auditory and practical perception is ensured, which contributes to the formation of complex competencies based on digital literacy.

7.6. Practical experience and approaches

The experience of developing digital literacy in an interdisciplinary integrated learning process, accumulated in Uzbekistan and abroad, confirms the effectiveness of innovative approaches and technological tools in education.

Practical experience of Uzbekistan

For several years, higher education institutions of Uzbekistan have been working on the digitalization of the educational process using platforms such as Ziyonet, electronic libraries, learning management systems (LMS) (Moodle, Edmodo, TestPortal.uz). In particular, interdisciplinary lessons are enriched with interactive tools (Padlet, Miro, Quizizz, Canva). These approaches:

Encourage students to study several subjects in an interconnected manner;

Promote the formation of independent thinking and analytical literacy;

It enables students to be involved in the learning process with digital tools at every stage.

Advanced international approaches

In the Finnish education system, at least 3-4 different digital and interactive tools are used simultaneously in each lesson. For example, animated explanations, group brainstorming (Jamboard), real-time assessment (Mentimeter) and video analysis (YouTube exercises) are used in parallel. This approach is based on multi-channel knowledge acquisition.

In US colleges, 100% of classes are conducted using digital platforms and assistants based on artificial intelligence. Students have the opportunity to work independently, analyze written assignments and receive automatic explanations on topics they do not understand through AI-based services such as ChatGPT, Grammarly, Khanmigo.

These practical approaches contribute to the formation of digital literacy not only as a technical skill, but also as a complex competence related to interdisciplinary thinking, independent decision-making and intellectual activity.

Conclusion

Theoretically, digital literacy is one of the competencies that underlie modern education. In particular, it includes such functional skills as independent work, analysis, research, as well as work with artificial intelligence and digital technologies. Effective development of this competence is ensured by an interdisciplinary integrated educational environment and advanced software. Advanced software is a personalized, flexible, interactive digital platform for students based on artificial intelligence, which allows for convenient organization of independent learning, control, analysis and assessment of educational activities. Pedagogical approaches focused on learning based on problem situations and scientific activity develop students' independent thinking, interest in research and analytical potential in the digital environment. High efficiency of these approaches is achieved when combined with artificial intelligence and digital platforms.

Interdisciplinary integration is an indispensable methodological basis for the formation of digital literacy. Students prepare for real-world situations by understanding the connections between disciplines, taking a holistic approach to complex situations, and developing contextual thinking. The use of various tools during the lesson enlivens the learning process, adapts learning and creates an educational environment that meets the needs and intellectual level of each student. In particular, artificial intelligence technologies and multimedia tools are the basis of the education of the future.

Practical classes are one of the most powerful tools for implementing digital literacy in life. Combining theoretical knowledge with practical activities, the student tests his level of knowledge, analytical abilities and decision-making skills based on solving real problems. Effective implementation of information and communication technologies (ICT) is not only the use of technical means, but also providing students with the opportunity to broaden their horizons, self-awareness, reflection, participation in social interaction and finding their place in the digital society. Therefore, the need to use advanced software to develop students' digital literacy based on interdisciplinary integration is becoming increasingly urgent. This, in turn, contributes to improving the quality of education, revealing the intellectual potential of students and shaping them as modern individuals capable of making independent and responsible decisions in life.

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